

EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER AS A MODERN MECHANISM OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Rapid technological changes, the development of information technologies, changes in the organization of work require graduates to have a wider range of skills and qualifications.*

The article highlights the tasks of state bodies, commercial structures, educational and scientific institutions and other civil institutions in the continuous education system that are part of educational clusters.

Keywords: *cluster, element, feature, activity, skill, team, element, structure, institution, organization.*

Currently, the continuing education system must meet the constantly changing needs of the labor market for specialists. Many educational institutions do not have information about the employer's requirements for specialists, what requirements should be placed on a graduate according to the employer's opinion, what the specialist's level of knowledge, skills and qualifications should be [5].

A group of researchers notes that the concept of continuous education appeared based on the concept of "Lifelong learning" (LLL) presented by P. Langrand in UNESCO documents in 1968 [4].

One of the priority tasks for the education system is "to further improve the continuous education system, to support and create conditions for the creative and intellectual potential of the young generation, to improve the learning content and formation mechanisms of pedagogical and didactic features of continuous education", and in this regard, education clusters are a modern mechanism of continuous education [1].

Rapid technological changes, the development of information technologies, and changes in the organization of work require today's graduates to have a wider range of skills and qualifications than before. In addition, skills that can be transferred from one field of activity to another are currently in growing demand. The role of communication and social skills, teamwork, decision-making skills, etc. is increasing.

The organization of educational clusters as a modern mechanism of continuous education is the basis for creating a new educational model. A real practical task gives purpose to the process of learning, provides motivation and material for mastering new organizational methodologies, introduces ideals, values, and cultural invariants into the social reality and decision-making process.

Studying the nature, structure, and characteristics of a cluster, D.I. Kalashnikov [3] considers the unification of the educational and production branches of the economy in it, that is, the network of educational organizations organized according to cluster principles and the grouping of business structures around this network [3] as a unique quality.

When describing the composition of clusters, it is necessary to describe the functional characteristics of its constituent elements. The elements of the educational cluster often include government bodies, commercial structures, educational and scientific institutions, and other civil institutions [3]. The presence of public authorities and other relevant organizations in the cluster is required to meet the special needs of the participants and to create a mechanism of cooperation described on the basis of the following positions:

1. The core of the cluster gathers participants represented not only by educational organizations and scientific centers, but also by commercial enterprises of various industries [3]. Thus, the core of the cluster unites two types of commercial enterprises, educational and scientific organizations around it. The main task of the core is to establish cooperation with commercial entities interested in cluster services [3].

2. The educational cluster provides the necessary conditions for the development of the field of technology and educational services by creating the necessary association of participants. In this regard, the technological specialization of commercial enterprises determines the direction of educational organizations [3].

Defines business production technology, which focuses on improving educational programs. The choice of technologies is provided by the latest advances in development and their availability, current skills of employees [3].

3. Continuing education institutions satisfy the demand of enterprises and organizations for specialized personnel. The task of educational organizations is to prepare competitive graduates for effective use in production. If education is based on current knowledge and continuity of education, it will be possible to solve this problem.

4. Enterprises use technologies (provided by leading universities or research institutes) in the process of creating their products, and employees receive the necessary expertise for their development. Accordingly, educational standards and training programs are established.

Table 1

Multitasking of the educational cluster

The mission of the educational cluster	Description
Coordinating task	Taking into account the specific characteristics of the region and the interests of the subjects of the educational process; transition from traditional strictly regulated forms of management to the level of joint management and self-management.
Synergistic task	Obtaining and growing synergistic effect, otherwise the complementary actions of a number of organizations, their sum is greater than the sum of individual results in a certain integrated system [6].
Prognostic task	Updating the philosophy of technical education in connection with the new social order of society, defines new requirements for its structure, content, quality, is aimed at increasing the professional training of students, forming a competitive person ready to constantly update their knowledge [6].

Leading task	Advanced development of the educational cluster is carried out by introducing new forms, methods, and innovative technologies into the activities of educational organizations.
Consolidation task	Uniting the "Education-Science-Production" integration system team in the conditions of the educational cluster, developing protection of its integrity as an independent association of people.
Corporate mission	Orientation of social partners of the educational cluster to common values and interests.
Information task	As a result of integration, education and production will be provided with new high-quality knowledge for the regular and rapid modernization of the economy and enterprises, as well as increase the qualifications of competitive personnel, because only due to the presence of educated and qualified personnel, it is possible to create, distribute and use the "wealth" of knowledge [6].
Reorganization task	Correcting and updating the process and content of vocational education, taking into account the requirements of society and the market economy; personal and professional development of students, providing them with knowledge and further education, employment, achieving their personal interests and creating opportunities for professional growth; acquisition of skills and competencies necessary to achieve professional excellence; obtaining qualifications that ensure equal participation of young and old population in the labor market; Creation of a system of vocational education in line with the European system; ensure their transition from one system to another; Vocational education within the general education segment that meets the requirements of the profession and the individual in professional self-improvement [6].

The effectiveness of the educational cluster depends on coordinated relations between the main subjects of the "education - science - production" integration system.

The main condition for successful development of entrepreneurship in the region is free access to resources, information and credit. Businesses can solve problems that arise when they enter clusters. The benefit that an individual enterprise receives from the development of a cluster largely depends on the characteristics of its business. In general, although costs can be reduced, flexibility and competitiveness can be increased in creating new products, technologies, and developing new markets for products [3].

In the process of continuing education, partner enterprises that are part of the educational cluster may be assigned the following obligations:

- preparing a forecast of the need for personnel, development of recommendations for directions of specialist training and opening of new specialties for educational institutions;
- to support the strengthening and development of the material and technical base of educational institutions, taking into account the training of specialists for enterprises;

- coordination of positions of social partners on vocational education issues;
- to ensure timely exchange of information, to support the creation of a single information field on the problems of providing enterprises with personnel;
- development of a program for adapting graduates to the labor force of enterprises.

Thus, the most important role in solving the existing problem and implementing professional education falls on employers, because, on the one hand, their competitiveness is based on qualified personnel, on the other hand, only enterprises can provide the necessary places for students for production and internship, can implement training programs in the output and formulate training requirements for competencies, skills and qualifications in terms of making necessary changes to reflect the changing requirements of the economy and scientific and technological progress. It is here that self-regulatory mechanisms should come into play, and employers and social partners should act as self-regulatory organizations, since staffing is an area of strategic interest of enterprises and organizations, along with other commercial interests.

The conditions for improving the quality of professional training of students of secondary special, vocational educational institutions within the framework of the educational cluster are as follows:

- analysis of qualification requirements imposed by employers on future specialists;
- consideration of specific interests of social partners;
- to increase their competitiveness by developing the volume and quality of educational services;
- marketing research of the modern labor market.

These conditions are the basis for the development of new requirements for the content of the continuous education process.

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